

**ASSESSMENT OF THE QUALITY OF LIFE OF PATIENTS WITH
ORTHODONTIC PATHOLOGY**

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Annotation. This article highlights the impact of oral health and dental aesthetics on the social life of patients, in particular the impact of orthodontic pathology on the quality of life. There is a direct link between a healthy bite and self-confidence. very often, patients who have any malocclusion, curvature of teeth and other orthodontic pathologies suffer from self-doubt and associate their complexes with this pathology. The purpose of this article is to assess the impact of malocclusion and aesthetics of the dentition on the social life of people.

Keywords: orthodontic pathology, malocclusion, social life

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INTRODUCTION

Dental diseases, including dentoalveolar anomalies, are among the most common in the world. According to various authors, up to 50–70% of the adult population of the world have certain dental anomalies and deformities. At the same time, in recent years there has been a tendency for an increase in the number of patients visiting an orthodontist not only to restore the function of the dentoalveolar system, but also aesthetics. Up to 50% of the adult population in Europe seek aesthetic dental treatment. Many studies have shown that aesthetic dentistry plays a key role in enhancing patients' sense of well-being, emotional stability, acceptance by others, success at work and in relationships with others.

MATERIALS AND METHODS. Turning to the clinic of aesthetic dentistry, many expect to increase their own self-esteem by improving aesthetic characteristics. One of the methods for assessing patients' perception of their own condition, patients' expectations from the upcoming treatment, as well as patients' perception of the treatment provided is the quality of life. The quality of life is an important concept not only for healthcare, but for all spheres of life in general, since the ultimate goal of the activity of all institutions of society is human well-being. This term has long been used in sociology, and since the 1960s. The term is also used in medicine.

Recently, the interest of scientists to the problems of dental health in ensuring the quality of life of people has steadily increased. The quality of life is understood as the ability of an individual to function in society in accordance with his position and to receive satisfaction from life. The quality of life is an integral indicator that reflects a person's assessment of the degree of his well-being, ability to function in society - his labor and social activities, personal life, brightness of the worldview, the ability to self-realization, etc. In addition, it abstractly

summarizes the whole complex of physical, emotional, mental and intellectual characteristics of the patient. The dependence of the level of quality of human life on the state of the dental system is largely determined by the functions assigned to it. Dental health determines the quality of nutrition, plays an aesthetic role and, to a certain extent, determines the well-being of the individual.

A subjective assessment of the quality of life, made by the patient himself, reflects his psychological status, the effectiveness of the treatment, allows you to determine the impact of the disease itself, as well as the treatment on the patient's condition. The assessment of the dental quality of life is determined by subjective indicators that illustrate the impact of oral health on the quality of life of a person along with an assessment of his need for dental services.

Dental quality of life is also defined as "a subjective assessment of the health of the oral cavity and the impact of its pathology on the function, as well as the mental and social status of an individual."

Assessment of the quality of life in dentistry is based on the completion of special questionnaires (questionnaires). Answers to the questions are filled in by the dentist or the patient himself. Usually, the questions are about how problems in the mouth affect the patient's physical well-being, his ability to eat well, communicate with other people, and perform social functions.

RESULTS. Assessment of the need for treatment based on subjective indicators is extremely important for planning the provision of dental services to the population, estimating costs and planning a strategy for further development of the dental services market.

The question of the influence of the severity of dentoalveolar anomalies and deformities on the level of quality of life remains interesting for study in scientific and practical terms.

As part of the study, a social survey was conducted among the population, mainly the younger generation. 141 people took part in the survey, the survey revealed that the majority of respondents have orthodontic pathology (malocclusion, curvature of teeth, absence of teeth, anomaly in the position of teeth). 68% of respondents stated that pathology negatively affects the quality of social life (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Survey results.

CONCLUSION

In the course of the study, indicators of the quality of life of healthy individuals, as well as patients with orthodontic pathology, were established. It has been established that the presence of orthodontic pathology significantly reduces the patient's quality of life. Orthodontic treatment performed can improve the quality of life of patients to values close to normal, even before the removal of the braces. The absence of positive dynamics of quality of life indicators or their insignificant severity can serve as an indicator of the patient's latent dissatisfaction with the treatment, even if there are no complaints from him at the moment. A detailed analysis of the questionnaire in combination with an additional examination of the patient in this situation helps to identify the "problem area" of orthodontic treatment and adjust its tactics before removing the braces, thus reducing the risk of complications, as well as complaints from the patient after it is completed.

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